

What are we dating – insights from the Ar-Ar geochronology of the Agly Massif, Southern France

Hoogendoorn, S.B.¹, Warren, C.J.¹

¹School of Environment, Earth and Ecosystem Sciences, The Open University, Milton Keynes MK7 6AA, UK, sander.hoogendoorn@open.ac.uk

Ar-Ar geochronology can be a powerful tool to extract information about the thermal history and cooling paths of high-grade metamorphic terranes. It is frequently assumed that Ar-Ar dates from such terranes reflect mineral-specific ‘closure temperatures’, formulated according to Dodson’s equation of thermal diffusion. However, this equation is only valid under certain conditions and requires validation of its underlying assumptions before it can be applied with confidence.

The Agly Massif, southern France, is a perfect example of a metamorphic terrane where a re-evaluation of the thermochronology is appropriate. The ~10-15 km long transect from the upper to the lower crust experienced a high temperature low pressure (HTLP) metamorphic imprint during Hercynian time. However, U-Pb monazite and apatite ages, as well as Ar-Ar biotite and muscovite ages, were unambiguously interpreted as cooling ages and linked to Cretaceous exhumation.

The main aim of this research is to investigate if the Ar-Ar geochronology of the Agly Massif does indeed reflect thermally activated volume diffusion or if other processes are more likely to explain the apparent Cretaceous overprint. To this end, we combine new in-situ and single-grain fusion Ar-Ar ages of biotite and muscovite from six representative samples throughout the area. Moreover, we compare these ages to diffusional models and evaluate them against detailed petrography and probe data.

Preliminary results indicate that single-grain muscovite and biotite ages define a range between ~115-95 Ma, with no statistical difference between the two minerals. This range cannot be explained by the internal uncertainty of the samples and cannot be mimicked through diffusional modelling, despite widely different PTt inputs. Petrographic observations reveal multiple retrograde reactions involving both feldspars and micas, despite many HTLP textures still prevailing. Our current view is that deformation and recrystallization significantly affected the Ar-Ar geochronology of the Agly Massif, governed through the local release and uptake of metamorphic fluids.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 956127

References:

- [1] Smith R (2011) *Min Dep* 47:303-322
- [2] Smith R and Jones P (2010) *Econ Geol* 105:443-798
- [3] Smith R et al. (2012) *Rev in Econ Geol* 17: 1-12